

ULTRADISPERSED NANOCOMPOSITES MEMBRANE OF COPPER@REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE/PVDF FOR ENHANCED THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

Li Shuang¹, Ye Li², Zhao Yan³

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191,
China

Keywords: Copper, Membrane, PVDF, Thermal conductivity

ABSTRACT

Poly (vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) is semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymer with excellent thermal stability, film-forming property and much more advantages over metal materials such as low density, corrosion resistance, integrated processing and low cost. So as to enhance its thermal conductivity, the nanoarchitecture of copper@reduced graphene oxide (RGO) was designed to improve it. The well-dispersion of graphene in PVDF and the synthesis of copper@RGO with different copper content were studied to improve the thermal conductivity of the nanocomposites. The nano copper was considered as the effective heat transfer medium to reduce the interface thermal resistance between graphene and PVDF chain segment. The graphene oxide (GO) was fabricated by modified Hummers method and the graphene was surface modified before used. Copper@RGO was fabricated by microwave liquid phase method. Then the copper@RGO were doped with PVDF to prepare membrane. The morphology, structure and thermal conductivity of the composite membranes with different additive content were characterized and analyzed. The thermal conductivity of composite membranes were significant improved with the addition of graphene. This tendency was further enhanced by the application of copper.